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CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR THE MONITORING OF ITALIAN UNMANAGED HONEY BEES: IMPLEMENTATION OF MEASUREMENT PROTOCOLS AND “BEE GUARDIANS” MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

La Citizen Science per il monitoraggio delle api italiane non gestite: implementazione dei protocolli di misura e dei sistemi di gestione dei “Bee Guardian”

Apis mellifera is a key species for biodiversity conservation thanks to its pollination service. For this reason, it has been defined as one of the most important species on the planet (HUNG *et al.*, 2018). The health status of this species is still difficult to assess: if globally the number of hives has increased by 45% in the last 50 years (FAO, 2009), this phenomenon is reversed in specific areas of the world such as in Europe (POTTS *et al.*, 2010). At the same time, increasingly, studies are reporting about the decline of wild bees and pollinators in general (BIESMEIJER *et al.*, 2006). In parallel, the International Union for Conservation of Nature declared insufficient data to evaluate the conservation status of *Apis mellifera* (IUCN, 2022). Considering these evidences, numerous projects have been launched for the collection of relevant information aimed to understand the survival of this species (e.g. Honey Bee Watch, MORO *et al.*, 2021).

With this mission in mind, and under the stimulus of the Honey Bee Watch network, in January 2020 was born the Resilient Bee project, a citizen science project which aims to monitor the survival of unmanaged honey bee colonies in Italy. Everyone who finds or knows an *Apis mellifera* unmanaged colony and desire to be part of the monitoring activity can subscribe to the project, becoming a “Bee Guardian”. Not only wild colonies but also colonies in apiaries can be registered. In the latter case,

artificial feed, use of chemical substances, little distance to other hives and operations that alter bees' natural behavior are prohibited after registration.

Each registered unmanaged colony is assigned to its Bee Guardian and a univocal alphanumeric code that identifies the colony is generated. Moreover a series of information on the colony are collected by the Bee Guardian: geographic place of the nest (municipality), kind of nesting site (i.e. a tree, a building), distance from the ground of the nest entrance, cardinal point of the nest entrance, habitat typology in the nearby area, kind of surrounding vegetation and possible neighboring apiaries.

In order to keep track of the colony's survival, each registered colony is monitored by the Bee Guardian in three temporal slots during the year: before swarming, after swarming and before wintering. Considering the variability of the Italian climate and its impact on the swarming season, the timing of each temporal slot slightly varies based on the climatic classification of Italian municipalities. Each temporal slot has a specific duration (1 month) and colonies that are not monitored in time are excluded from the project.

Monitoring should be done when the outside temperature is above 10 °C, in moderate wind conditions and in absence of rain. The Bee Guardian is asked to report information about the flight activity at the entrance of the nest, presence of pollen importation and presence of parasites. If no activity is detected, the Bee Guardian is asked to report the decease of the colony and no more monitoring activities are further required.

The data collection, as well as the indication of the monitoring timing, are carried out through an online platform and an online management system tailored to the needs of the project. Moreover, local supervisors assist the Bee Guardians in the activities and in the request of assistance.

In the first year of the project all the procedures were tested and improved. Seventy unmanaged colonies were reported and registered by the Bee Guardians. The most frequent places of settlement observed were walls (50%), followed by trees (26%), beehives (7%) and other artificial structures (7%). The most frequently reported habitat was the forest (37%), followed by the agricultural countryside (25%), urban centers (22%), natural countryside (9%) and parks (4%). To date, 50% of the registered colonies have been excluded from the project due to natural death, abandonment of the nest or lack of monitoring by the Bee Guardian.

The next steps involve a substantial recruitment of new Bee Guardians in order to increase the sampling sites, along with the improvement of monitoring methodology and its predictive validity, based on the critical issues emerged in the first trial year.

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